

Metadata management

Metadata

... is a concise set of data, required to identify, describe, and manage your data.

Why is it needed?

To enable humans and machines to find, access, reuse, transform and combine data from different sources

Metadata schema

A set of rules for structuring and describing metadata.

Standards

The most popular standards for metadata schema are Dublin Core, Data Cite, DCAT and more.

Fact sheet

- Pomerantz, J., Metadata. The MIT Press (2015). JSTOR, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt1pv8904>.
- Wilkinson, M., et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci Data 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- Enke, H., Tokareva, V. PIDs in the Natural Sciences (1.0). Zenodo (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368436>
- Redelbach, A., Curation & Metadata Schemes for Dynamic Filtering. <https://results.punch4nfdi.de/files/documents/report-D-TA5-WP2-1.pdf>
- Popular metadata standards/frameworks:
 - **Dublin Core:** "Dublin Core Metadata Element Set, Version 1.1." Dublin Core Metadata Initiative, 2020, <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dces/>. (Accessed 19 Mar. 2025.)
 - **DataCite:** DataCite Metadata Working Group. "DataCite Metadata Schema for the Publication and Citation of Research Data, Version 4.5." DataCite, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.14454/3w3z-sa82>. (Accessed 19 Mar. 2025.)
 - **Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT):** The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). "Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) – Version 3." Edited by Alejandra Gonzalez-Beltran et al., W3C, 2023, <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>. (Accessed 19 Mar. 2025.)
 - **Resource Description Framework (RDF):** The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). "RDF 1.1 Concepts and Abstract Syntax." Edited by Richard Cyganiak, David Wood, and Markus Lanthaler, W3C, 2014, <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf11-concepts/>. (Accessed 19 Mar. 2025.)

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